

VALKYRIES

D1.19 Ethics and diversity compliance report M24

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a report on ethics and diversity compliance requirements met from the VALKYRIES Consortium during the project.

The deliverable includes a demo with scenarios to be broadly used while developing technological solutions for first responders.

The demo has been shared in open access on the VALKYRIES website and updated considering the feedback received by stakeholders during the ethical legal workshops and through one-to-one communications.

This document is an updated version of D1.6. The new content with respect to the D1.6 has been highlighted in yellow for easy review and identification.

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Ethics and diversity compliance report M24

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3. Document and Project Scope

This document answers harmonisation and standardisation needs in the field of compliance activities impacting on the whole life-cycle of the research and in particular on the ethical legal issues related to non-discrimination and diversity issues. **It is the updated version of D1.6 submitted at M12.**

3.1. Project Overview

VALKYRIES aims to develop standardised and harmonised procedures for first responders. In this frame, ethical legal issues shall be addressed by design to support any step of the technological development. For this reason, this deliverable will contribute to identify, assess and extract harmonised practices for innovators.

3.2. Document Structure

This document includes a general overview of the methodological approach towards ethics and diversity compliance; the description of the issues emerged in the project; the extraction of guidelines and best practices for innovators. The document includes a web-based demonstrator (DEMO).

4. Ethics and diversity compliance report

4.1. Methodological remarks

Challenges to diversity protection are many: they include non-discriminatory actions aiming to prevent prejudices occur as well as those positive actions aiming to support diversity in a given environment.

To this end, we design this deliverable in a double perspective: firstly, as a compliance activity addressed within VALKYRIES consortium during the entire life-cycle of the research; secondly, as an opportunity to develop a more inclusive environment within a project Consortium, addressing ethics and diversity as a management tool.

The two perspectives have been addressed through a bottom-up approach developed with a series of initiatives aiming to analyse the ethics and diversity-related issues both in VALKYRIES project and in general in Research and Innovation sector. In particular, we developed the following initiatives:

1. We performed a **continuous ethical-legal assessment** of the project activities. The ethical-legal unit (SSSA), in fact, is involved in all the WPs to address the following issues and detect ethics and diversity challenges in terms of compliance.
2. We provided an analysis on the contents of the **Gender Equality Plans** adopted by the individual partners of the consortium.
3. We provided the collection of **ethics and diversity needs** from the Consortium in order to assess perceived barriers to ethics and diversity as well as possible strategies to prevent and deal with possible issues.
4. We completed the analysis with an analysis of further tools to address ethics and diversity in R&D&I sectors.

The one-to-one and plenary consulting activities under sub 1 has been undertaken during the development of tasks, deliverables, etc. allowing to shape a concrete overview of sensitive topics, sectors, and challenges within the VALKYRIES ecosystem. Together with the collection of data under sub 2, 3, and 4, we explored how to address the ethics and diversity challenges both in VALKYRIES and, more generally, in a research Consortium as well as to discuss how to develop efficient solutions to be practically implemented in a web-based tool.

4.2. Ethics and Diversity analysis

Such an analysis starts from the premises that strictly compliance activities are considered to develop a cultural change aiming to undertake a more ethical and inclusive research *by design*, by promoting good practices.

For the purposes of this deliverable, in order to avoid overlapping with other tasks under WP 1, 3 and 8, we will focus only on the following grounds: gender-related issues and other diversity related issues.

1. **Gender-related issues** we mean, according to the European Institute for Gender Equality – EIGE (2014) notion: *“all aspects and concerns related to women’s and men’s lives and situation in society, to the way they interrelate, their differences in access to*

and use of resources, their activities, and how they react to changes, interventions and policies”¹.

- 2. Other diversity-related issues** with the aim to reduce bias under all possible grounds of discrimination. In this context, we apply the grounds of discrimination according to article 9 of the EU Regulation General Data Protection Regulation “GDPR” notion of special categories of personal data as those ones that are “revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership (...) genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person’s sex life or sexual orientation”. In particular, we dealt with the concept of vulnerability in the digital dimension in order to distinguish those that are usually exposing individuals and groups to possible risks, including the specific risks emerging in the digital environment from those that are specifically and solely addressed as digital ones.

4.2.1. Continuous ethical-legal assessment

As anticipated, the continuous ethical legal assessment for gender-related and other diversity-related issues has been undertaken by providing ethical legal advice during the life-cycle of the VALKYRIES research to meet also other compliance requirements as well as to develop a more inclusive culture within the consortium.

The following issues have been addressed during the project in terms of human resources and activities management:

1. To promote the gender balance within the appointments to be distributed in the project. For example, during the Kick of Meeting 2 women have been appointed respectively as innovation manager and communication manager.
- 2. To promote a better work-life balance during the management of the project. For example, calls and meetings have been scheduled combining family needs (e.g., avoiding / limiting schools breaks) and agenda have been followed taking into account possible individual needs of family care. Also plenary meetings have been planned in order to allow all Consortium members to come back home as soon as possible by concluding the agenda by lunch of the second day and always allowing to remotely join in order to catch the flights.**
- 3. To promote inclusiveness and non-discrimination also considering that both research and development activities are characterised by data-driven solutions.**

In the development of technical tasks, instead, gender-related and diversity issues have been addressed as follows.

1. In the development of questionnaires delivered to first responders: no reference to gender identity / sexual orientation has been included in light of the principle of minimization under article 5 GDPR. In fact, the consortium considered as not relevant such an information for the purposes of the task.
2. The Consortium considered that as far as data collection in the context of the developed Minimum Dataset for the victims, information regarding sex and pregnancy status will be processed for healthcare purposes and management only.

¹ European Institute for Gender Equality – EIGE (2014). Effectiveness of Institutional Mechanisms for the Advancement of Gender Equality: Review of the Implementation of the Beijing Platform for Action in the EU Member States.

3. The Consortium considered the possible digital divide and digital vulnerabilities also in the development of harmonised training programmes and pre-standardisation activities. In fact, the lack of digital skills and data-driven culture in the first response activities might increase risks of exposing fundamental rights of consortium members, users, and stakeholders.

In the development of AI-based solutions, gender-related and diversity issues are considered following the EU Commission strategy for a Trustworthy AI.

In particular, the harmonisation and standardisation actions for innovators cannot avoid the current debate on technologies assessment under the ethics, lawfulness and robustness pillars identified by the High-Level Group on AI. In parallel to the proposal on AI Regulation, in fact, a series of tools and checklists have been developed to address the compliance activities in an ethically manner by design and by default. The so-called Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) checklist, for instance, drives the developers through a questionnaire of 63 questions addressing seven grounds of analysis that include, among all, also diversity, non-discrimination and fairness. The latter aims to avoid unfair bias and to ensure accessibility and universal design, including stakeholders' participation in the development steps. In this regard, VALKYRIES project addressed these requirements as follows.

ALTAI Requirements	Questions to be addressed	Implemented actions and relevant task
Avoidance of unfair bias	Did you establish a strategy or a set of procedures to avoid creating or reinforcing unfair bias in the AI system, both regarding the use of input data as well as for the algorithm design?	The VALKYRIES project aims to prevent bias by providing balanced samples to the algorithms, aiming to generate unbiased models.
Avoidance of unfair bias	Did you consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and/or subjects in the data? Did you test for specific target groups or problematic use cases? Did you research and use publicly available technical bias that are state-of-the-art, to improve your understanding of the data, model and performance? Did you assess and put in place processes to test and monitor for potential biases during the entire lifecycle of the AI system (e.g. biases due to possible limitations stemming from the composition of the used data sets (lack of diversity, non-representativeness)? O Where relevant, did you consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and or subjects in the data?	The project considers training models with a balanced number of users, taking into consideration diversity characteristics of the society. It also considers the use of state-of-the-art techniques to ensure that data is well balanced and provide biased results.
Avoidance of unfair bias	Did you put in place educational and awareness initiatives to help AI designers and AI developers be more aware of the possible bias they can inject in designing and developing the AI system?	The designers and developers of the project have been helped through many meetings to understand the consequences of unfair bias

ALTAI Requirements	Questions to be addressed	Implemented actions and relevant task
		and possible solutions to avoid it.
Avoidance of unfair bias	Did you ensure a mechanism that allows for the flagging of issues related to bias, discrimination or performance of the AI system? O Did you establish clear steps and ways of communicating on how and to whom such issues can be raised? O Did you identify the subjects that could potentially be (in)directly affected by the AI system, in addition to the (end-)users and/or subjects?	VALKYRIES considers some mechanism obtained from experience and state-of-the-art in order to prevent the generation of biased models. It has also established clear step and ways of communication which has been studied in depth by all contributors and end-users. The project identifies as subjects that could be affected all the entities that belong to this.
Avoidance of unfair bias	Is your definition of fairness commonly used and implemented in any step the process of setting up the AI system? Did you consider other definitions of fairness before choosing this one? Did you consult with the impacted communities about the correct definition of fairness, i.e. representatives of elderly persons or persons with disabilities? Did you ensure a quantitative or metrics to measure and test the applied definition of fairness? O Did you establish mechanisms to ensure fairness in your AI system?	The definition proposed by VALKYRIES is being applied in all phases of models generation. The project also identified many possible definitions before choosing the one which is being used. It consulted with all the entities on which this project depends and to which it is addressed. The project performed many tests to check if the definition used is valid, applying balanced samples and techniques provided by state-of-the-art. VALKYRIES establishes mechanisms that allow to guarantee the fairness through tests and studies of the generated models.
Accessibility and Universal Design	Did you ensure that the AI system corresponds to the variety of preferences and abilities in society?	The project has raised the awareness of all entities in charge of the AI system so that it can correspond to preferences and abilities in society.
Accessibility and Universal Design	Did you assess whether the AI system's user interface is usable by those with special needs or disabilities or those at risk of exclusion? O Did you ensure that	The AI system user interface has been designed and implemented with the

ALTAI Requirements	Questions to be addressed	Implemented actions and relevant task
	information about, and the AI system’s user interface of, the AI system is accessible and usable also to users of assistive technologies (such as screen readers)? O Did you involve or consult with end-users or subjects in need for assistive technology during the planning and development phase of the AI system?	objective of making it easy for all people to use. Moreover, the project ensured that every user who needs help to use the AI system user interface since it implemented assistive technologies such as screen readers, text readers and speech input software.
Accessibility and Universal Design	Did you ensure that Universal Design principles are taken into account during every step of the planning and development process, if possible?	VALKYRIES considered the use of Universal Design principles during all Systems Development Life Cycle (SDLC) phases.
Accessibility and Universal Design	Did you take the impact the AI system on the potential end-users and/or subjects into account? Did you assess whether the team involved in building the AI system engaged with the target end-users and/or subjects? Did you assess whether there could be groups who might be disproportionately affected by the outcomes of the AI system? Did you assess the risk of the possible unfairness of the system onto the end-user’s or subject’s communities?	The project always considers the possible consequences, both positive and negative, that may be caused by the AI system. It also evaluated that designer and developer are involved with the target in order to check if the requirements are correct and new requirements are needed. VALKYRIES project took into account that those people with disabilities could be the most affected for the results. For this reason, it has been provided with mechanisms to avoid this problem. It also evaluated the possible risks and it established mechanism so that the risk is avoided or minimized.
Stakeholder Participation	Did you consider a mechanism to include the participation of the widest range of possible stakeholders in the AI system’s design and development? Did you consider vulnerable persons (including those with disabilities) among stakeholders?	The project considered that the communication with many stakeholders allows to know new useful requirements that have to be implemented.

Table 1 – ALTAI requirements

4.2.2. Gender Equality Plans analysis

Among the partners, we collected and analysed the following Gender Equality Plans (GEP) in order to identify analogies and differences as well as to extract possible best practices to be applied in the Consortium strategy for ethics and diversity issues management.

The following table summarises the grounds of the undertaken analysis.

AREA	Objectives	How VALKYRIES supported these Actions
Work-life balance	Support for the reconciliation of work and private life	Work organisation tailored to family needs
	Adoption of the gender perspective in organizational culture	Supporting women recruited in the project
	Adoption an inclusive language protocol	Adoption of gender-neutral language
	Building an inclusive work and study environment	Adoption of inclusive strategies during formal and informal activities
	To promote feminine leadership among the Administration and Services Staff	Project Boards have been gender balanced
Gender balance in top positions and in decision-making bodies	Harmonization of decision-making processes and internal sources with the activities included in the GEP	Project Boards have been gender balanced
	Promote equal opportunities in culture, processes and institutional practices	Project Boards have been gender balanced
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	Improvement of equal opportunities in academic recruitment	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
	Improvement of equal opportunities in career progression	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
	To transmit the commitment to gender equality and non-discrimination	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
	Job stability and promotion	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
	To reduce the pay gap	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
Integration of the gender dimension in research and	Promotion of the integration of sex and gender variables in the research process	Ethical-legal impact assessment in the development of the VALKYRIES ecosystem
	Promote the integration of a gender dimension in teaching content	N/A

AREA	Objectives	How VALKYRIES supported these Actions
teaching programs	To transmit the commitment to gender equality and non-discrimination through the University's	N/A
	Showcasing and encouraging research with a gender perspective	Website contents highlight the gender perspective in VALKYRIES development and management
Tackling gender-based violence, including sexual harassment	Contribute to the reduction of gender prejudices and stereotypes	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
	Raise awareness on issues related to gender equality within the community of the organisation and outside it, also contributing to the deconstruction of gender stereotypes	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
	Prevent, identify and manage cases of sexual harassment between teaching staff, technical staff and administrative, students and female students	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
	To showcase resources against harassment	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
Encouraging diversity and inclusion	Everyone shall perform at its best in order to ensure that workforce grows and remains diverse in regards to cultures, gender, generation, abilities and other capacities	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
	To guarantee balanced presence on governing bodies and representation	Issue addressed during KoM

Table 2 – GEPs analysis

4.2.3. Ethics and diversity needs

In order to detect ethics and diversity needs among the Consortium, we mapped its composition, the adoption of an internal GEP and the emerged gender-related issues in VALKYRIES.

The table below summarises the results of the data collection on gender-related issues.

Partner	Team composition	Gender Equality Plan	Gender related issues	Adopted strategy
SSSA	1 M (including unit coordinator) 5 F	Yes	Pregnancy of a recruited researcher.	flexible timesheet; back-up plans and temporary hiring

Partner	Team composition	Gender Equality Plan	Gender related issues	Adopted strategy
IND	16 M (including project coordinator) 6 F	Yes	N/A	N/A
KEMEA	5 M (including the unit coordinator) 8 F	In progress	N/A	N/A
SERMAS	10 M; 8 F	No	Pregnancy of a recruited researcher.	Flexible timesheet
NOV	5 M 0 F (before 4 M - 1 F)	Yes	N/A	N/A
HRT	5M 4F	Yes	N/A	N/A
HESE	2M (including tasks coordinators) 2F	Yes	N/A	N/A
PARTICLE	5M 1F	No	N/A	N/A
UMU	7M (researchers) 3F (admin)	Yes	N/A	N/A
ISEMI	3 M, 3 F	No	N/A	N/A
ARATOS.NET	3 M 1 F	Yes	N/A	N/A
Blockchain 2050	4M 3F	Yes	N/A	N/A

Table 3 – GEPs and Teams analysis

In addition, we asked partners to suggest possible actions to mitigate gender and diversity related gaps. The following propositions have been identified.

- Introduction of specific costs in the budget for family-related issues for recruited staff (e.g., babysitter, caregiver)
- Adoption of selected strategies at University level: flexitime, economic equity
- Make a longer shortlist when recruiting
- Use skills-based assessments
- Adopt Community Principles and a Code of Conduct
- Appoint a Safety Officer
- Mentorship program
- Focus groups
- Balanced recruiting candidate lists

- Give Benefits for Participating in Diversity Programming
- Conduct timely audits

4.2.4. Further grounds of diversity assessment an analysis.

Within the context of ethics and diversity assessment further grounds shall be analysed in the management of a research life-cycle that are not only related to the gender dimension. To this end, we analysed the ethical legal profiles related to the persons with disabilities and the ones related to the data-driven and digital environment. The DEMO check-list has also been integrated by these profiles in order to complete the assessment within the different phases of the life-cycle of the research.

4.2.4.1. Persons with disabilities.

First of all persons with disabilities are often excluded as they face multiple barriers when taking part in Research and Development life-cycles. Barriers and enablers to cultural participation have been identified as follows. 1) lack of effective/adequate legislation, policies and legal standards; 2) lack of funding and/or of adequate services; 3) negative attitudes; 4) lack of accessibility; 5) lack of consultation with, and involvement of, persons with disabilities. This is true in the field of culture² and it could find application also for Research and Development sector.

In this regard, the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and its Optional Protocol (A/RES/61/106) was adopted on 13 December 2006, turns considering persons with disabilities as subjects, and not anymore as “objects” of charity, medical treatment and social protection. It enhances their rights, and in particular the ones of claiming, making decisions for their lives based on their free and informed consent as well as being active members of Society. In this regard, also according to article 31 of the Convention (on Statistics and Data Collection) and the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), people with disabilities shall be included in all aspects of development-focused work, including research and development where the ethical implications must be considered carefully.

Individuals with disabilities face a higher probability of unemployment compared to those without disabilities. This situation often leads to heightened emotional strain and heightened experiences of physical or social isolation, ultimately impacting their overall quality of life. The field of disability studies is hindered by inadequate funding, resulting in a lack of comprehensive research into the challenges faced by people with disabilities. Moreover, the inclusion of individuals with disabilities in clinical trials is frequently neglected. In 2011, the World Health Organization and the World Bank Group published the inaugural World Report on Disability, which presented a series of recommendations aimed at dismantling accessibility barriers and fostering the active engagement of people with disabilities within society. In particular, to “strengthen and support research on disability” and to “involve people with disabilities” are the main recommendations.

From this perspective, it is relevant to address since the very beginning of the research life-cycle inclusiveness also in projects that are not directly related to deal with epidemiology, rehabilitation, public policy etc. Discussing issues affecting people with disabilities during

² A. Leahy - D. Ferri, Barriers and Facilitators to Cultural Participation by People with Disabilities: A Narrative Literature Review, 2022, DOI: 10.16993/sjdr.863.

research priority agenda-setting meetings could raise awareness enriching the content of the general ethical principle on “Do no harm”.

As far as other grounds of diversity assessment are concerned, no issues have been identified within the VALKYRIES Consortium and therefore none of the above-mentioned issues required to be addressed and mitigated.

The following methodological recommendations have been therefore identified:

1. Encourage the involvement of persons with disabilities in the life-cycle of the research both in the recruitment procedures and in the stakeholders engagements
2. Collect and raise awareness among the team/consortium on specific needs for disabled persons engaged in the projects
3. Implement tailored safeguards to overcome practical barriers
4. Provide reporting and monitoring mechanisms in order to timely address possible issues

4.2.4.2. Digital vulnerabilities and vulnerabilities in the digital environment

A person can be considered as a vulnerable subject for a combination of factors affecting her life and existence, putting her at risk with respect to a number of identifiable circumstances (natural or not), including to belong to a minority or to a group considered as vulnerable in a given historical moment.

The digital transition of services, products and relationships impacted on the development of mechanisms of protection for fundamental human rights, also because new risks have emerged (and are emerging), shaping new digital vulnerabilities – like the case of cybersecurity issues – or new dimensions of known risks that may require different safeguards in the digital environment.

For example, in the scenario of the patient expressing consent to a given healthcare digital solution aiming to support diagnoses, or treatment services, or pathways of rehabilitation. In such cases, it is necessary to adapt the implementation of tailored actions aiming to mitigate the digitalised risks.

The impact on fundamental rights refers to the lack of transparency or awareness of the subject with respect to data processing operations (such as, for example, profiling of secondary habits or behaviours of the same) involving on the progressive loss of control of information flow.

Specifically, what is to be the subject of the probability for the subject to suffer negative consequences, even unforeseeable, from the processing of personal (and other) data in the digital dimension. Between the most common scenarios, in this regard, boil down to: information concerning the data subject, as well as the classification of his profile in certain categories of users resulting in direct (or indirect) exposure to content or automated decisions for purposes not necessarily attributable to those that gave rise to the collection of data.

The interest on the matter arises from the number of legislative initiatives of the European Union's on data and digital market strategies. The same are structured in such a way as to identify roles and responsibilities among the different actors of a given data flow, in order to better identify and assess what impact on the respective activity it may have towards users, as such, or users as per se categories vulnerable subjects, so that different levels of compliance can be imposed on specific obligations aimed at protecting the recipients of the service or product put on the market. In this regard, the impact assessment on data protection pursuant to article 35 EU Reg. n. 2016/679, hereinafter GDPR, or all those that are based on artificial intelligence

techniques, or to the obligations of c.d. due diligence on online content established by the Digital Service Act are fruitful examples of this trend.

Within the management of VALKYRIES project, the role of the digitalisation is paramount both in the research development and management. In this regard, the continuous ethical-legal assessment has been addressed to identify potential digital vulnerabilities and vulnerabilities in the digital environment during the life-cycle of the research in order to protect both the members of the consortium, stakeholders and users.

The following methodological recommendations can be addressed:

1. Identify possible digital vulnerabilities within the impact assessment
2. Assess their impact on fundamental rights protection during the life-cycle of the research
3. Identify and implement proper safeguards to mitigate/avoid the identified risks
4. Check whether further risks might be identified in the digital dimension from general-related vulnerabilities
5. Assess also in this case the impact of the identified risks and implement proper safeguards
6. Develop reporting and monitoring mechanisms in order to timely address possible issues

5. DEMO: How to address ethics and diversity compliance in Research and Development sector

The DEMO includes two main sections to explore how to address ethics and diversity compliance in Research and Development sector: 1. Managing the life-cycle of the research, including four subsections 1. Preparatory activities; 2. Research Development; 3. Dissemination and the Research Team Management section in order to develop an inclusive Consortium.

A first version of the DEMO has been already published at M12 in the VALKYRIES website <https://www.valkyries-h2020.eu/Demo.html> and presented to tailored ethical and legal workshops and events where stakeholders provided inputs and suggestions to improve its functionalities.

A revised version is released and embedded to the platform developed in D1.5.

5.1. Section 1: Managing the life-cycle of the research

5.1.1. Preparatory activities

During preparatory activities the researcher has to start an impact assessment identifying risks that the proposed idea could develop against fundamental rights and in particular against inclusiveness. Therefore, the researcher has to identify proper technical and organisational measures to design fair and accountable solutions by design and by default as well as to build up managing procedures able to ensure ethical values and diversity promotion among the human resources involved in the project. To this end, the following actions shall be undertaken.

In order to assess the proposal in terms of impact on human dignity and non-discrimination, verify if it is required, firstly:

- a. to include an ethical-legal expertise among the team to undertake the ALTAI check-list if you are developing a solution based on Artificial Intelligence
 - i. if yes, allocate resources and justify them
- b. to include the data protection officer to assess the impact on personal data processing
 - i. if yes, allocate resources and justify them
- c. to include a cybersecurity assessment and management
 - i. if yes, allocate resources and justify them
- d. the approval of an ethical committee to test the solution
 - i. if yes, allocate time and resources and justify them

Then:

- e. to develop a workplan including
 - i. a continuous assessment of the impact on fundamental rights and cybersecurity threats
 - ii. the implementation of safeguards to mitigate the identified risks against human dignity and inclusion
 - iii. monitoring and report mechanisms to face unpredicted risks

5.1.2. Research development

In order to promote equality and diversity in the developed technology:

- a. Assess the grounds of discrimination in the data collection and justify them in order to avoid bias in the automated decision-making
- b. Assess the grounds of discrimination in the data processing activities in order to avoid bias in the automated decision-making
- c. Check the data generated by the automated decision-making in order to avoid further bias

5.1.3. Dissemination

During the dissemination activity the role of ethics and diversity is crucial as the accountable approach could be promoted together with the developed technology. This would increase the trustworthiness among the given technological solution as well as contributing to create standards also in the ethical dimension in terms of inclusiveness and non-discrimination.

Therefore, it will be useful to:

- a. Disseminate disaggregated data on sex in order to highlight possible vulnerabilities/bias or to promote best practice
- b. Promote safeguards and practices developed in the life-cycle of the research to contribute on the standardisation and harmonisation process

5.2. Section 2: Research Team Management

In order to promote equality and diversity in the team:

- a. Apply within the project principles adopted in the institutional Gender Equality Plans / Codes of Ethics / other self-regulatory procedures on ethics and diversity enhancement
- b. Assess the level of diversity in your consortium and apply measures to establish an inclusive environment during the life-cycle of the research and development (e.g. work-life balance in the workplan; feminine inclusion and leadership in the governance, etc), by:
 - Mapping gender representation in the team/Consortium
 - Mapping inclusiveness in the key-activities and roles of the project
 - Mapping possible minorities in the team/Consortium
 - Mapping possible needs in the given need
 - Mapping the different religious-cultural holidays
- c. Apply measures to overcome existing barriers
 - Provide training to overcome possible digital divide;
 - Provide training to overcome cultural barriers;
 - Arise awareness on the concept of “do no harm” regarding possible minorities included in the team/consortium (sexual orientation, religion, philosophical opinion, disabilities, economics, etc.)
- d. Develop a monitoring/reporting mechanisms in order to timely address possible issues with flexibility.

6. Conclusions

This deliverable described the VALKYRIES approach towards ethics and diversity compliance, providing a useful demonstrator applicable to all research and innovation contexts during the entire life-cycle of the research, **including the consortium management profiles.**

7. Annex A – References and bibliography

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8. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALTAI	Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
EIGE	European Institute for Gender Equality
EU	European Union
GDPR	General data protection regulation
GEP	Gender equality plan

Table 4 – Glossary